

IMPLEMENTATION OF GREEN RENEWABLE HYDROGEN ENERGY PRODUCTION THROUGH OPTIMIZED ALKALINE ELECTROLYSIS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15427359>

Abstract. *The transition to green and renewable hydrogen energy is a vital step in combating climate change and ensuring sustainable energy systems. This study investigates the optimization of alkaline water electrolysis in a clean and renewable method of hydrogen production by analyzing the effect of potassium hydroxide (KOH) electrolyte concentration using cost-effective steel electrodes. Experimental results aim to identify optimal operational parameters to maximize hydrogen yield while minimizing energy consumption, supporting the development of scalable, eco-friendly hydrogen generation technologies.*

Keywords: *Green Hydrogen, Renewable Energy, Alkaline Electrolysis, Energy Efficiency, KOH Concentration, Sustainable Energy Production.*

Introduction

As the world transitions towards clean energy, hydrogen has emerged as a promising energy carrier, capable of supporting a variety of applications from transportation to industrial processes. Alkaline electrolyzers represent one of the most cost-effective methods of producing hydrogen, using simple materials and well-established technology. The efficiency of significant interest in hydrogen as a potential fuel. Alkaline electrolysis, a well-established technology, offers a sustainable pathway to hydrogen production by splitting water into hydrogen and this process is influenced by various factors, including the electrolyte concentration and electrode material.

This research delves into the optimization of alkaline electrolysis, a promising technology for hydrogen production. We investigate the impact of varying KOH electrolyte concentrations on the performance of alkaline electrolyzers utilizing steel electrodes. By combining experimental and practical approaches, we aim to identify the optimal electrolyte concentration for maximizing hydrogen production while minimizing energy consumption. Our analysis will focus on key performance indicators such as Faraday efficiency, cell voltage, and overall energy efficiency. The comprehensive investigation will provide valuable insights into the design and operation of efficient alkaline electrolyzers [1].

Material and methods.

Voltage Efficiency is the ratio of the theoretical minimum voltage required for electrolysis to the actual applied voltage. It measures how effectively the applied voltage is utilized to drive the electrochemical reaction.

$$\text{Voltage Efficiency, } \eta_v (\%) = \left(\frac{V_{\text{Theoretical}}}{V_{\text{Actual}}} \right) * 100\%$$

We assessed the performance of our alkaline electrolyzer using voltage efficiency, the ratio of the theoretical minimum voltage (1.23 V for hydrogen production) to the actual applied voltage.

This theoretical voltage is derived from the Gibbs free energy change of the water splitting reaction, which is 237 kJ/mol of hydrogen. By dividing this energy change by the number of electrons involved (2 moles of electrons per mole of hydrogen) and multiplying by the Faraday constant (96,485 C/mol), we obtain the theoretical voltage of 1.23 V. The actual voltage is always higher due to various energy losses, including ohmic losses, activation overpotential, and concentration overpotential. By identifying and minimizing these losses, we can improve the overall efficiency of the electrolyzer [1–3].

Faradaic Efficiency is the ratio of the actual amount of product produced to the theoretical amount, based on the amount of charge passed through the electrolyte. It indicates how efficiently the electrical current is converted into the desired chemical product.

$$\text{Faradaic Efficiency, } \eta_f (\%) = \left(\frac{\text{Actual } H_2 \text{ L/min}}{\text{Theoretical } H_2 \text{ L/min}} \right) * 100\%$$

Faradaic efficiency is a crucial metric for evaluating the performance of alkaline electrolyzers. It quantifies the ratio of the actual amount of hydrogen produced to the theoretical amount, calculated using Faraday's law, based on the charge passed through the electrolyte. Factors such as side reactions, ohmic losses, mass transport limitations, and electrode kinetics can negatively impact Faraday efficiency. Therefore, optimizing performance, strategies like adjusting electrolyte concentration, selecting suitable electrode materials, improving cell design, and controlling operating conditions can be employed to minimize losses and maximize hydrogen production [1,4].

Energy Efficiency is the ratio of the energy content of the produced hydrogen to the electrical energy input. It measures the overall efficiency of the electrolysis process in converting electrical energy into chemical energy stored in hydrogen.

$$\text{Energy Efficiency, } \eta_{\text{Cell}} (\%) = \eta_V \times \eta_F$$

Energy efficiency can help to determine overall cell performance by dividing the energy content of the produced hydrogen by the power consumption. This calculation provides a measure of how effectively the input electrical energy is converted into chemical energy stored in hydrogen [1,5].

The alkaline electrolyzer's hydrogen gas compartment, separator, and oxygen gas compartment are crucial for efficient and safe hydrogen and oxygen production through water electrolysis. The hydrogen gas compartment collects hydrogen produced at the cathode, ensuring separation from oxygen. The separator, typically made of materials like zirconia-based ceramics or polymer membranes, prevents gas mixing while allowing ion conduction. The oxygen gas compartment collects oxygen produced at the anode. The electrolyzer uses an alkaline electrolyte (KOH or NaOH) and electrodes (nickel or nickel-oxide coated) to facilitate the process. The separator ensures high-purity gases, and optimized designs minimize resistance and improve energy efficiency [5,6].

While potassium hydroxide (KOH) is commonly used as the electrolyte in alkaline electrolyzers, its concentration and the choice of electrode material play crucial roles in determining the overall performance. This work delves into the effects of different KOH concentrations on the performance of alkaline electrolyzers utilizing steel electrodes [7]. Steel electrodes offer several advantages for alkaline electrolysis. They are relatively inexpensive, making them a viable option for large-scale hydrogen production [8]. Steel electrodes can withstand harsh alkaline environments, exhibiting good corrosion resistance and high mechanical

strength. This allows for robust cell designs. Moreover, steel possesses good electrical conductivity, facilitating efficient electron transfer during the electrolysis process. In return, the performance of steel electrodes can be influenced by factors such as surface roughness, porosity, and the formation of oxide layers. Optimizing the electrode surface and selecting the appropriate steel alloy can further enhance their performance [9].

Efficiency in the electrolysis process is critical, and innovative approaches are being explored to enhance alkaline water electrolysis [10]. Impurities in the electrolyte can impact the efficiency of water electrolysis, particularly in alkaline electrolyzers with high concentrations of potassium hydroxide [11]. It is essential to consider the electrolyte, cathode, and anode components in the design of water electrolyzers to optimize efficiency [12]. Research has also shown that high-performance alkaline water electrolyzers based on catalysts can achieve enhanced Faradaic efficiency [13].

Results.

To study the impact of electrolyte concentration on alkaline electrolyzer performance, a series of experiments were conducted. The experimental setup consisted of a six-cell alkaline electrolyzer with 316L stainless steel electrodes and KOH solutions of varying concentrations (10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%). KOH solutions were prepared by carefully adding solid KOH pellets to pure water. To ensure complete dissolution and prevent potential damage to the electrolyzer components due to excessive heat generation, the addition process was slow and gradual. After preparation, the solutions were allowed to cool for at least 10 minutes before being added to the electrolyzer cells.

Figure 1. One-cell of six electrodes.

The electrolyte temperature was maintained at a constant value to minimize temperature effects. We used a power source (ADC-3303D) to adjust the current density and measure the actual voltage, allowing us to evaluate its impact on cell voltage and energy efficiency. The voltage was stable and fixed for every concentration to calculate the power consumption and hydrogen amount. A flowmeter (SD-6000) was used to measure the volume of hydrogen gas produced. Theoretical calculations were performed to gain insight into the underlying mechanisms and to optimize the electrolyte concentration and electrode material. By maintaining a consistent temperature and current density, hydrogen output was measured using a calibrated flowmeter. Theoretical and experimental data were compared to validate the effectiveness of each electrolyte concentration in real-world, renewable-powered systems.

Figure 2. Renewable-powered system with alkaline electrolyzer that was used to optimize hydrogen energy production.

The experimental results demonstrate that the electrolyte concentration and the use of steel electrodes significantly impact the performance of alkaline electrolyzers. Higher electrolyte concentrations generally lead to improved conductivity, resulting in lower cell resistance and higher current densities. However, excessively high concentrations can lead to increased ohmic losses and reduced efficiency. Our findings indicate that a 30% KOH solution provides an optimal balance, maximizing hydrogen production without compromising efficiency. Concentrations beyond 30% did not yield significant improvements and may even accelerate corrosion processes (Table 1).

As shown in Table 1, increasing the KOH concentration enhances Faradaic efficiency and hydrogen output. Specifically, Faradaic efficiency increased from 68% at 10% KOH to 88% at 30% KOH, while hydrogen production rose from 0.371 L/min (liters per minute) to 0.478 L/min. These results confirm a positive correlation between electrolyte concentration and electrolyzer performance. However, diminishing returns in hydrogen output beyond 30% suggest that excessively high concentrations may offer limited advantages and could lead to increased material degradation. For instance, while 30% KOH achieves the highest Faradaic efficiency, the slight performance gain compared to 40% may not outweigh the potential risks of corrosion.

Graph 1. The relevance of Faradaic efficiency to KOH concentration.

In addition, steel electrodes, while offering cost-effectiveness and durability, may exhibit lower catalytic activity compared to noble metal catalysts. In contrast, through appropriate surface treatments and optimization, their performance can be improved. By comparing the performance of electrolyzers with different KOH concentrations and electrode materials, the optimal combination for maximizing hydrogen production and minimizing energy consumption can be identified.

KOH Concentration	Faradic Efficiency (%)	Actual H ₂ Output (L/min)
10%	68%	0.371
20%	77%	0,422
30%	88%	0.478
40%	85%	0.456

Table 1. Comparative summary of hydrogen output.

Results showed that higher KOH concentrations improve conductivity and reduce resistance, which supports increased hydrogen production—an essential factor for viable green energy solutions. A concentration of 30% KOH delivered the best balance between performance and stability, achieving a Faradaic efficiency of 88% and producing 0.478 L/min of hydrogen, with minimal energy losses and no excessive corrosion.

These findings highlight the potential of using affordable steel electrodes and optimized KOH solutions for environmentally friendly and cost-effective hydrogen generation. When integrated with renewable power sources like solar or wind, this method offers a sustainable and scalable alternative to fossil-fuel-based hydrogen production.

Conclusion

This study provides valuable insights into the effect of electrolyte concentration and steel electrode utilization on the performance of alkaline electrolyzers. By carefully selecting the appropriate concentration and optimizing operating conditions, it is possible to enhance the efficiency and reduce the cost of hydrogen production through alkaline electrolysis.

Future research efforts should focus on further exploring the optimal concentration range, the performance of different steel alloys, and the development of advanced surface treatments to achieve even greater improvements in performance and durability.

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